

Report of a Rare Case of a Congenital Cutaneous Syndrome

Mariana Meneses^{1*}, Duarte Flor², Leonor Ramos²

¹Pediatrics Department, Hospital Pedro Hispano – Unidade Local de Saúde de Matosinhos

²Dermatology Department, Hospital Pediátrico – Unidade Local de Saúde de Coimbra

Citation: Mariana Meneses, Duarte Flor, Leonor Ramos. Report of a Rare Case of a Congenital Cutaneous Syndrome. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2025;4(1):1-9.

Received Date: 15 January, 2025; **Accepted Date:** 18 January, 2025; **Published Date:** 20 January, 2025

***Corresponding author:** Mariana Meneses, Department of Pediatrics, Hospital Pedro Hispano, Rua Dr. Eduardo Torres, 4464-513 - Matosinhos, Portugal

Copyright: © Mariana Meneses, Open Access 2025. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour*(ICMCRJ) (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Vascular anomalies encompass a diverse group of conditions, some of which are part of complex syndromes with potential systemic implications. Phakomatosis pigmentovascularis (PPV) is a rare congenital syndrome characterized by the coexistence of vascular malformations and dermal melanocytosis, classified into five types based on cutaneous features and systemic involvement.

Case Report: We describe a 4-month-old female infant with capillary malformations, cutis marmorata telangiectatica congenita (CMTC), and dermal melanocytosis distributed across the gluteal region, back, shoulders, and upper limb. These findings led to a diagnosis of type II + V PPV. No systemic abnormalities or neurodevelopmental delays were observed, and the patient's familial history was unremarkable. The clinical diagnosis underscores the importance of early identification, multidisciplinary management, and longitudinal follow-up to monitor potential systemic complications.

Discussion: PPV results from post-zygotic mosaic mutations in the GNAQ and GNA11 genes, which affect vasomotor and melanocytic development. Diagnosis relies on clinical evaluation of characteristic skin manifestations. Although type II PPV is the most common subtype, systemic involvement such as neurological, ocular, or skeletal abnormalities can alter the prognosis. Management involves targeted imaging and referral to appropriate specialties based on findings.

Conclusion: This case highlights the unique presentation of type II + V PPV, emphasizing the necessity of vigilance in follow-up due to the potential for evolving systemic manifestations that may influence classification and prognosis.

CASE-REPORT

INTRODUCTION

Vascular lesions, including vascular neoplasms and vascular malformations, are common in newborns¹. Although most of these lesions are benign, some may be part of complex syndromes or systemic disorders or may be associated with complications. The 2018 classification of the *International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies* divides vascular anomalies into 5 categories. Vascular malformations associated with other anomalies is one of them, which includes Sturge-Weber syndrome, Klippel-Trenaunay syndrome, macrocephaly-capillary malformation, Proteus syndrome, CLOVES syndrome (congenital lipomatous overgrowth, vascular malformations, epidermal nevi, spinal/skeletal anomalies/scoliosis), phakomatosis pigmentovascularis and Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome. This case reports one these rare congenital syndromes, predominantly consisting of capillary malformation, cutis marmorata and congenital telangiectasia (CMTC) and dermal melanocytosis

Case report: A 4-month-old female infant with no noteworthy gestational history is the result of a full-term, eutocic birth that has adapted well to extra-uterine life. Somatometry was adequate for gestational age, and the neonatal period was uneventful. However, at birth, there were capillary malformations on the right gluteal region and dermal melanocytosis on the gluteal region with no further abnormalities on objective inspection. Echocardiography and transfontanelar ultrasonography were required (with no changes), and the patient was referred to a pediatric dermatology. At her dermatological checkup, at 4-months-old, she exhibited multiple blue-grey macules and patches on the gluteal region, upper back, shoulders, and upper limb, indicating dermal melanocytosis (**Figure 1**). The patient also showed irregular erythematous patches on the back and gluteal region, consistent with capillary malformations (**Figure 2**), as well as violaceous reticulated lesions on the left lower limb, suggestive of CMTC (**Figure 3**). No health complications were observed since birth and normal neuropsychomotor development was assessed. There was no history of parental consanguinity nor similar cases in the family. This resulted in the diagnosis of type II + V phakomatosis pigmentovascularis (PPV), according to Hasegawa's and Happle's classification.

Figure 1. Blue-grey patches and macules on upper back, shoulders, and upper right limb

Figure 2. Erythematous irregular erythematous patch on the gluteal region

Figure 3. Violaceous reticulated lesions on the left lower limb

DISCUSSION

PPV is a rare congenital syndrome characterized by the association of a capillary malformation with dermal melanocytosis (Mongolian spot, nevus of Ota), CMTC, nevus spilus, or epidermal nevus. Nevus anemicus and café-au-lait spots can be associated findings [2].

Due to its rarity, the prevalence is currently unknown [2]. The etiology is thought to be a mosaic developmental abnormality of the vasomotor nerves and melanocytes (derived from the neural crest). It is caused by sporadic mutations in GNA11 and GNAQ genes, which encode G α subunits of heterotrimeric G proteins. These genetic mutations have been detected in affected tissues, but are undetectable in the blood, suggesting it is a post-zygotic mosaic disorder. The diagnosis is clinical, based on the combination of associated cutaneous findings [4].

There are five types of PPV, distinguished based on cutaneous signs (**Table 1**). Each type is further divided into subtypes A and B, depending on whether there is systemic involvement (evident in subtype B). Type II (cesioflammea) is the most common type (port-wine stain with dermal melanocytosis) [2,5,6]. In a small proportion of patients, PPV has been associated with a variety of systemic abnormalities, such as neurologic complications (seizures, cerebral atrophy, intracranial vascular abnormalities calcifications), ocular involvement (glaucoma, naevus of Ota), skeletal abnormalities (limb length discrepancies, scoliosis) and renal agenesis [2,3].

Management should include imaging evaluation (renal and abdominal ultrasound; brain MRI) and referral to other specialties depending on clinical findings [6,7] (e.g. ophthalmology if naevus of Ota is present). No treatment is required for the capillary malformation or dermal melanocytosis, only for

cosmetic reasons, where laser treatment can be used ⁶. The outcome depends upon the presence of another associated conditions ^[6-8].

Table 1. Types of phakomatosis pigmentovascularis ^[6]

Type	Clinical features
I	Capillary malformation, epidermalnaevus
II (Cesioflammea)	Capillary malformation, dermal melanosis (lumbosacral dermal melanocytosis, nevus of Ota)
III (Spilorosea)	Capillary malformation, naevus spilus, naevus anaemicus
IV (Unclassified)	Capillary malformation, dermal melanosis (lumbosacral dermal melanocytosis, naevus of Ota), naevus spilus, naevus anaemicus
V (Cesiomarmorata)	Cutis marmorata telangiectatica congenita, dermal melanosis (lumbosacral dermal melanocytosis, naevus of Ota)

CONCLUSION

The case reported presents manifestations that classify it as type II + V PPV: extensive bilateral capillary malformations, aberrant Mongolian spots and the presence of cutis marmorata telangiectatica congenita. To this day, the patient has not presented systemic involvement. However, the importance of follow-up should be emphasized, since systemic alterations can become evident with time, changing the classification and prognosis.

REFERENCES

1. Kanada KN, Merin MR, Munden A, Friedlander SF. A prospective study of cutaneous findings in newborns in the United States: correlation with race, ethnicity, and gestational status using updated classification and nomenclature. J Pediatr. 2012;161(2):240-245.
2. Fernández-Guarino M, Boixeda P, de Las Heras E, Aboin S, García-Millán C, Olasolo PJ. Phakomatosis pigmentovascularis: Clinical findings in 15 patients and review of the literature. J Am Acad Dermatol. 2008;58(1):88–93.
3. Huang C, Lee P. Phakomatosis pigmentovascularis IIb with renal anomaly. Clin Exp Dermatol. 2000;25(1):51-54.
4. Thomas AC, Zeng Z, Rivière JB, O'Shaughnessy R, Al-Olabi L, et al. Mosaic Activating Mutations in GNA11 and GNAQ Are Associated with Phakomatosis Pigmentovascularis and Extensive Dermal Melanocytosis. J Invest Dermatol. 2016;136(4):770-778.
5. Hasegawa Y, Yasuhara M. Phakomatosis pigmentovascularis type IVa. Arch Dermatol. 1985;121:651.

6. Happle R. Phacomatosis pigmentovascularis revisited and reclassified. Arch Dermatol 2005;141:385.
7. Shin H, Kim YG, Kim YE, Park H. Clinical characteristics, and treatment of 52 cases of phacomatosis pigmentovascularis. J Dermatol. 2019;46(10):843–848.
8. Tran C, Alward WLM. Phacomatosis Pigmentovascularis. Ophthalmol Glaucoma. 2021;4(3):250.